

**SYNTHESIS OF 7-METHOXY-3-METHYL-1-TETRALONE AND ITS
OXIDATION WITH SELENIUM DIOXIDE**

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7-Methoxy-3-methyl-1-tetralone has been synthesised, which on oxidation with selenium dioxide gives 7-methoxy-3-methyl-2-hydroxy-1:4-naphthoquinone.

In connection with experiments on a colouring matter, being investigated in this laboratory, it was thought necessary to synthesise 7-methoxy-3-methyl-1:2-naphthoquinone (II). Further, compounds of this structure are expected to possess some interesting physiological properties. Weygand and Schröder (*Ber.*, 1941, 74B, 1844) have oxidised 3-methyl-1-tetralone by selenium dioxide and obtained 3-methyl-2-hydroxy-1:4-naphthoquinone (phthiocol) and 3-methyl-1:2-naphthoquinone. Following a similar procedure the 7-methoxy-3-methyl-1-tetralone (I) was oxidised by selenium dioxide, but the only pure product which could be isolated was 7-methoxy-3-methyl-2-hydroxy-1:4-naphthoquinone (III).

4-Methoxy- α -bromopropiophenone (Hell and Holtenberg, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 688) on condensation with ethyl malonate gave an ester, which on hydrolysis with alcoholic potassium hydroxide yielded α -(4-methoxybenzoyl)-ethylmalonic acid. This on decarboxylation gave β -(4-methoxybenzoyl)-butyric acid (m.p. 155°), which on Clemmensen's reduction gave β -(4-methoxybenzyl)-butyric acid. The acid chloride of β -(4-methoxybenzyl)-butyric acid on cyclisation by anhydrous aluminium chloride yielded 7-methoxy-3-methyl-1-tetralone (b.p. 190°-192°/30 mm.). Its oxidation by selenium dioxide yielded 7-methoxy-3-methyl-2-hydroxy-1:4-naphthoquinone (m.p. 174-75°). A deep red gum was also obtained, which, however, could not be purified.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation of α -(4-Methoxybenzoyl)-ethylmalonic Acid.— α -Bromo-4-methoxypropiphenone (Hell *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) (50 g.) was added to the suspension of the sodium salt, prepared from powdered sodium (6 g.) and ethyl malonate (32 g.) in dry benzene. It was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 hours. This resulting ester was directly hydrolysed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide for 3 hours and the product obtained was worked

up yielding α -(4-methoxybenzoyl)-ethylmalonic acid. (Yield of the crude product was 20 g.). The semi-solid acid, thus obtained, was purified by dissolving it in sodium bicarbonate and regenerating it by acidification. It was kept in ice for 3 hours, when a granular solid was obtained. It is soluble in ether, acetone, alcohol, and sparingly soluble in benzene and chloroform. It was crystallised from chloroform in needles, m.p. 155°. (Found: Equiv., 133.9; C, 58.6; H, 5.4. $C_{13}H_{14}O_6$ requires equiv., 133; C, 58.64; H, 5.2 per cent).

Preparation of β -(4-Methoxybenzoyl)-butyric Acid.— α -(4-Methoxybenzoyl)-ethylmalonic acid (15 g.) was decarboxylated at 160° in vacuum for 1 hour. The gummy semi-solid was taken up with ether and filtered. The ether was removed and the acid was purified by dissolving it in sodium bicarbonate, followed by acidification. The acid solidified after keeping it in a desiccator for a few days. It was crystallised from petroleum ether in needles, m.p. 70-71°. It is soluble in ether, chloroform, acetone, benzene and alcohol, and sparingly soluble in petroleum ether. (Found: Equiv., 224; C, 64.8; H, 6.4. $C_{12}H_{14}O_4$ requires equiv., 222; C, 64.86; H, 6.3 per cent). Semicarbazone, m.p. 186°. (Found: N, 15.2. $C_{13}H_{17}O_4N_2$ requires N, 15.0 per cent).

Preparation of β -(4-Methoxybenzyl)-butyric Acid.—To freshly prepared zinc amalgam (80 g.), taken in one litre flask, hydrochloric acid (conc., 100 c.c.) was added and then β -(4-methoxybenzoyl)-butyric acid in toluene (30 c.c.) was added immediately. It was refluxed for 80 hours and then the product was worked up as usual. The acid, thus obtained, was distilled under reduced pressure, b. p. 185°-188°/20 mm. (Found: Equiv., 210; C, 69.1; H, 7.7. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2$ requires equiv., 208; C, 69.2; H, 7.6 per cent). Anilide, m. p. 91°. (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{18}H_{21}O_2N$ requires N, 4.9 per cent).

Preparation of 7-Methoxy-3-methyl-1-tetralone.—To β -(4-methoxybenzyl)-butyric acid (8 g.) freshly distilled thionyl chloride (40 c. c.) was added. It was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 hours and the excess of thionyl chloride removed and the acid chloride distilled under reduced pressure, b. p. 138-140°/40 mm.

The acid chloride (6 g.) was dissolved in dry and freshly distilled carbon disulphide (20 c. c.) and the mixture was transferred to a round-bottomed flask carrying a calcium chloride guard tube. Anhydrous aluminium chloride (6 g.) was added to it in small lots when gaseous hydrogen chloride was evolved. It was kept at room temperature overnight, and on the next day it was heated on a water-bath till the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased. It was then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. The oily layer which separated was extracted with ether and washed with 10% sodium hydroxide solution and finally with water. The ether extract was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and the ether removed. The tetralone, thus obtained, was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 190°-192°/30 mm. (Found: C, 75.4; H, 7.5. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 75.7; H, 7.3 per cent). It gave a semicarbazone, m.p. 245°. (Found: N, 16.9. $C_{13}H_{17}O_2N_2$ requires N, 17.0 per cent).

Preparation of 7-Methoxy-3-methyl-2-hydroxy-1:4-naphthoquinone.—7-Methoxy-3-methyl-1-tetralone (1.8 g.) was dissolved in 20 c.c. of boiling alcohol and selenium dioxide (3.6 g.) was then added to it and the mixture refluxed for 6 hours, when all the selenium settled at the bottom of the flask. The selenium was removed by filtration

and the filtrate concentrated. It was then poured into ice-cold water when a red solid separated which was filtered and dissolved in ether and extracted with alkali. The ether extract (A) was worked up separately. The alkaline extract was separated and acidified when a yellow granular solid separated. It was then taken up in ether and washed with water. The ether extract was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and the ether removed. The yellow solid obtained was crystallised from benzene in plates, m.p. 173-74°. The yield of the pure product was 0.3 g., m.p. 174-75°. It is soluble in ether, chloroform, acetone and alcohol, and sparingly soluble in benzene and petroleum ether. It gave a red coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 65.6; H, 5.5. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 65.46; H, 5.4 per cent).

On reductive acetylation it gave a triacetate, m.p. 176°. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 5.5. $C_{18}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 62.4; H, 5.3 per cent).

Product obtained from Ether extract (A).—On removal of ether, a deep red gum was isolated, but it did not crystallise nor did it give a semicarbazone.